

CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION ON THE LEAVES OF *GYMNEMA SYLVESTRE* R. Br.

By HARI NARAYAN KHASTGIR, SUDIENDU KUMAR SENGUPTA AND PASUPATI SENGUPTA

Lupeol, β -amyirin, stigmasterol and an amorphous antisaccharine principle have been isolated from the leaves of *Gymnema sylvestre* R. Br.

The leaves of *Gymnema sylvestre* R. Br. (Sanskrit: Meshashringi) of N.O. Asclepiadaceae possess antisaccharine property and are used in the Ayurvedic system of medicine as an antidiabetic agent. In a recent review Mukerji (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, 16A, 477) has given an account of the medicinal use and the antisaccharine property of the plant along with the past chemical investigations carried out with it. Although considerable amount of investigations have been carried out with the leaves of the plant, still no crystalline compound except cyclitol (Posternak and Schopfer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1950, 23, 343) and tartaric acid (Chopra, "Indigenous Drugs of India," Art Press, Calcutta, 1933, p. 320) has been characterised. It is also not certain whether the amorphous substance, described as gymnemic acid (see above reference) by Hooper is a single substance or not. Further, Hooper's claim that gymnemic acid constituted the antisaccharine principle of the leaves has been challenged (Power and Tutin, *Pharm. J.*, 1904, 89, 234; Chopra *et al.*, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1928, 16, 115).

Because of its medicinal importance, we became interested in a systematic investigation of the leaves of the plant. The dried and powdered leaves were first extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) to give a brown resinous mass. After repeated chromatography and crystallisation we have been able to isolate from this resinous mass the triterpene alcohols, lupeol and β -amyirin and the plant sterol, stigmasterol. It may be pointed out, however, that if lupeol and β -amyirin, occur together in the same plant, it is extremely difficult to separate them. In fact, scandol, m.p. 161-63°, $[\alpha]_D + 56^{\circ}.9$, once believed to be a triterpene alcohol (Simonsen, "Terpenes", The University Press, Cambridge, 1957, Vol. IV, p. 442) has recently been proved to be an intimate mixture of lupeol and β -amyirin (Corey, Proskow and Parks, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1957, 46, 183).

After extraction with petroleum ether, the leaves were extracted with 95% ethyl alcohol. This extraction gave a water-soluble, brown, viscous gum which was partitioned between water and a mixture of chloroform and ethanol (2:1), when the chloroform-ethanol solution extracted the antisaccharine principle of the leaves. The antisaccharine principle, obtained as an amorphous powder, has so far resisted all attempts at crystallisation. Further investigations on this antisaccharine principle is in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Extraction and Chromatography.—Dried and powdered leaves of *Gymnema sylvestre* R. Br. (600 g) were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) for 8 hours. The solvent was distilled off, leaving a brown resinous mass (14.5 g-), which was chromatographed over 500 g. of alumina and the following broad fractions were collected :

Fraction I	Petroleum ether eluate with increasing proportion of benzene up to petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) eluate.	Waxy material, 6 g.
Fraction II.	Benzene eluate.	Partially solid material, 2.6 g.
Fraction III.	Benzene : ether (1 : 1) eluate.	Partially solid material, 1.4 g.

Further elution with more polar solvents did not yield any crystalline material.

Fraction II: Isolation of Lupeol and β -Amyrin Acetate.—Fraction II (2.6 g.) was chromatographed over 200 g. of activated alumina and after a forerun of 1.1 g. of a gummy material, petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 2) eluate gave two fractions : (A) 0.19 g. of a crystalline solid, m.p. 160–185°, followed by (B) 0.32 g. of a crystalline solid, m.p. 140–60°.

Lupeol.—Fraction A on repeated crystallisation from methanol and then from acetone gave colorless crystals, m.p. 212–13°, $[\alpha]_D + 27^\circ.7$. The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of lupeol did not show any depression.

Lupeol Acetate.—The above solid, m.p. 212–13°, was treated with acetic anhydride and pyridine as usual, when lupeol acetate crystallised from the reaction medium. The crystals were filtered and recrystallised from acetone. The analytical sample melted at 214–15°, $[\alpha]_D + 47^\circ.6$. The melting point was not depressed when mixed with an authentic sample of lupeol acetate. (Found : C, 82.32 ; H, 10.95. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.99 ; H, 11.12%).

β -Amyrin Acetate.—Fraction B (0.32 g.) in the above chromatogram was repeatedly crystallised from methanol and then from acetone, when 0.18 g. of colorless crystals, m.p. 164–66°, $[\alpha]_D + 51^\circ$ (see scandol in the theoretical portion) were obtained. The crystals were acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine as usual, when an acetate crystallised out from the reaction medium. It was filtered and crystallised from acetone, when colorless crystals, m.p. 236–38°, $[\alpha]_D + 84^\circ.8$, were obtained. This acetate did not depress the melting point of an authentic sample of β -amyrin acetate. (Found : C, 81.81 ; H, 10.87. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.99 ; H, 11.12%).

Fraction III: Isolation of Stigmasterol.—Fraction III (1.4 g.) was rechromatographed over 50 g. of alumina when the benzene eluate gave 0.32 g. of a solid material, which on repeated crystallisation from methanol and then from acetone gave colorless crystals, m.p. 165–70°, $[\alpha]_D - 48^\circ.3$. The constants reported for stigmasterol (Fieser and Fieser, "Natural Products Related to Phenanthrene", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1949, p. 95) are m.p. 170° and $[\alpha]_D - 49^\circ$.

Stigmasterol Acetate.—The above solid was converted into the acetate in the usual manner. The acetate after crystallisation from methanol and then from acetone, melted at 142° , $[\alpha]_D - 54^{\circ}$. The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of stigmasterol acetate did not show any depression. (Found : C, 81.91 ; H, 10.95. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{50}O_2$: C, 81.88 ; H, 11.08%).

Stigmasterol benzoate was prepared in the usual manner, m.p. $159-60^{\circ}$, $[\alpha]_D - 27^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 83.60 ; H, 9.92. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{52}O_2$: C, 83.66 ; H, 10.14%).

Isolation of the Amorphous Antisaccharine Principle.—Dried leaves of *Gymnema sylvestre* R. Br. (600 g.), after extraction with petroleum ether, were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with 95% ethyl alcohol for 24 hours. The solvent was removed and the brown viscous gum was dissolved in 100 c.c. of water and extracted with ether. The aqueous solution was then extracted thrice with 100 c.c. portions of a mixture of chloroform and ethanol (2:1). The combined chloroform-ethanol solution was once washed with 50 c.c. water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated. The amorphous residue, thus obtained, was taken up in methanol, charcoaled and evaporated, when 8.5 g. of the amorphous antisaccharine principle was obtained. The solid lost the antisaccharine property in contact with aqueous hydrochloric acid and precipitated another amorphous substance, presumably the gymnemic acid of Hooper. The antisaccharine principle was chromatographed over silica gel. But all attempts at crystallisation have failed so far.

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